

Friction Perception on Fine and Coarse Textured Surfaces

Maja Fehlb^{1,2}^[0000-0002-1827-2333] and Roland Bennewitz^{1,2}^[0000-0002-5464-8190]

¹ INM Leibniz-Institute for New Materials, Saarbrücken, Germany
roland.bennewitz@leibniz-inm.de, maja.fehlb@leibniz-inm.de

² Physics Department, Saarland University, Saarbrücken, Germany

Abstract. Fingertip friction plays a key role in tactile interactions, but the perception of friction in active touch has rarely been studied. In this psychophysical study, we examine the impact of feature sizes on micro-structured surfaces on friction perception. First results indicate that the perception of friction differences is deteriorated when a surface with structures smaller than 100 μm is compared with larger structures, possibly in agreement with the two pathways proposed in Katz' duplex theory of tactile perception.

Keywords: Fingertip Friction · Friction Perception · Duplex Theory.

1 Introduction

Friction perception plays a significant role in our daily tactile interactions with surfaces and objects, influencing tasks such as grasping, manipulation, and active exploration. Katz' duplex theory of tactile perception postulates that tactile signals are processed through two distinct channels: the spatial channel, which encodes skin deformation by coarse structures larger than 100 μm , and the temporal channel, which encodes skin vibrations originating also from smaller fine structures [1]. The stimulation of mechanoreceptors by deformation and vibration then leads to the signals in the somatosensory cortex which are interpreted as tactile perception [2]. Our previous work suggests that the ability to perceive frictional differences between pairs of samples decreases when one sample carries only a fine texture with features smaller than 100 μm [3]. Here we present an experiment that further investigates the impact of fine and coarse structures on the perception of friction in active touch with the goal to reveal a possible role of spatial and temporal perception channels.

2 Experimental Method

We prepared two groups of micro-structured rubber samples with hexagonal arrays of pillars with different dimensions. Group *A* had a fine texture of pillars with diameter [μm] and height [μm] of 40/80, 40/120, 60/120, and 60/180. Group

B had a coarse texture of pillars with 100/200, 100/300, 150/350, 150/450. All samples were made of the same material (polyurethane, PMC 770, Smooth-On, Inc., Pennsylvania) and were produced by replica molding technique. The distance between pillars was equal to their diameter, so that the flat tops of the micro-pillars covered 22.6 % of the surface for all samples.

We chose 21 sample pairs, including combinations within groups A and B , as well as between the two groups. These sample pairs were presented to nine right-handed participants (5 female, aged 21 to 57, avg. age 31). Participants explored the samples in circular movements with their straight dominant index finger to answer the question: "*For which of the two samples is it more difficult to move the finger over the surface*". In this forced-choice task, participants could switch between the two samples as often as they wanted before answering. Participants wore noise-reducing headphones, and the samples were behind a blurring screen to prevent sound or vision influencing their decision. The sample pairs were placed on a 3-axis force sensor (K3D120 with GSV-8 amplifier, ME-Messysteme, Germany) to track the normal force (F_N) and the lateral forces (F_x, F_y) of the finger during the exploration.

3 Results

The participants explored the samples with a median speed (v) between 14 and 197 mm/s (avg.: 68.97 ± 39.7 mm/s) and with circle radii between 1.4 and 20.4 mm (avg.: 8.27 ± 2.9 mm). The median normal force (F_N) on the sample was between 0.2 and 3.5 N (avg.: 0.9 ± 0.6 N). Exploration frequencies varied among sample pairs, with one to nine touches per sample.

The coefficient of friction (μ) for all sample explorations with a normal force higher than 0.1 N was calculated using $\mu = F_F/F_N = \sqrt{F_x^2 + F_y^2}/F_N$. For further analysis, we use the median coefficient of friction of all touches made on each sample during the exploration of the sample pair.

We separate the set of sample pairs into two categories: intra-group comparisons, i.e. comparisons between samples from either group A with fine texture or from group B with coarse structures, and inter-group comparisons, which involve one sample from group A and one from group B . For the intra-group comparisons we measured a mean relative difference in μ of 7 % with a maximum difference of 33 %, and for the inter-group comparisons, the mean difference was 10 % with 48 % as the maximum difference. Note that there is large overlap in friction differences between intra- and inter-group comparisons.

The ability of participants to rank the perceived friction in agreement with the measured $\Delta\mu/\mu$ for the actual sample pair is summarized in the psychometric curves shown in Fig. 1. The intra-group comparisons resulted in a just noticeable difference (JND) for friction of 24 %, while the inter-group comparison show a JND of 49 % for friction differences. It was thus more difficult for participants to compare friction between samples with fine and samples with coarse texture than between samples of either fine or coarse texture, despite the fact that the average friction difference was even higher in the inter-group comparisons.

Fig. 1. The probability that participants answered in agreement with the measured coefficient of friction is plotted against the relative difference in friction coefficient $\Delta\mu/\mu$. a) Summary of sample comparisons within groups *A* and *B*. b) Summary of comparisons between the groups. The data are fitted with a Weibull sigmoid function ranging from 0.5 to 1. The intersection with the 75% limit indicates the just noticeable difference in friction coefficient.

Following the concept of Katz’ duplex theory, the tactile perception on the fine textures could be dominated by vibrations, while spatial cues dominate on coarse textures. Ranking friction between samples which stimulate two different sensory channels might be more difficult for the participants than ranking pairs of samples where only one type of sensory impression dominates. Our results suggest that a difference in texture size across the threshold scale of $100 \mu\text{m}$ deteriorates participants’ perception of friction.

In our experiment, the relative friction differences are mostly lower than the JND. The small relative differences result from the high friction values observed on the micro-structured rubber samples (average μ : 2.34). For a full study on friction perception on fine and coarse textures, we will not only invite a larger group of participants but will also explore if the application of lubricants on the samples can produce larger relative differences in friction for the comparisons.

Acknowledgments. This work was supported by the Volkswagen Foundation.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

References

1. Hollins, M., Risner, S. R.: Evidence for the duplex theory of tactile texture perception. *Perception & Psychophysics*, 62(4), 695-705 (2000).
2. Lieber, J. D., Bensmaia, S. J.: Emergence of an invariant representation of texture in primate somatosensory cortex. *Cerebral Cortex*, 30(5), 3228-3239 (2020)
3. Fehlberg, M., et al.: Perception of Friction in Tactile Exploration of Micro-structured Rubber Samples. In: Seifi, H., et al.: *EuroHaptics 2022, LNCS*, vol. 13235, pp. 21-29. Springer, Cham (2022)